

Appendix

(a) first half

(b) second half

(c) even members

(d) odd members

Figure A1: MPI-ensemble, sub-samples. Welch's periodogram (ensemble mean, lines, right y-axis) of the data for the whole time series (black), the first (blue), second (green) and last (red) 40 years of the time series. E-folding time plotted against frequency, derived from feedback matrices L for each period (dots, left y-axis).

Figure A2: MPI-ensemble, LIM fitted to each member (1-68). Welch's periodogram (ensemble mean, lines, right y-axis) of the data for the whole time series (black), the first (blue), second (green) and last (red) 40 years of the time series. E-folding time plotted against frequency, derived from feedback matrices L for each period (dots, left y-axis).

